

Analysis of Service Level of Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya Corridor 2 Based on Importance Performance Analysis and Customer Satisfaction Index

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ABSTRACT: Trans Metro Pasundan is an integrated highway bus system serving the Greater Bandung metropolitan area, West Java. This service is a program from the Ministry of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia through the Directorate General of Land Transportation, and Bandung is the eighth service after Makassar and Banyumas in the Bus Friends Buy the Service (BTS) service purchasing program. The purpose of this study is to assess the operational performance and user satisfaction of the Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 Greater Bandung transportation system, as well as to identify service conditions based on World Bank standards and Ministerial Regulation No. 29 of 2015. A sample of 105 respondents was selected from a population of 369,320 Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 passengers using the Slovin's formula. The research findings indicate that the load factor and travel time meet the standards, although some load factors do not meet the criteria. Priorities for improving passenger satisfaction include providing facilities at shelters/stops, availability of polls, among others. The Customer Satisfaction Index of 73.078 suggests that passengers are "Satisfied" with the service performance.

KEYWORDS: Trans Metro Pasundan, Indeks Performance Analysis, Customer Satisfaction Index, Satisfaction, Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Transportation is interconnected with economic growth and is an essential aspect of distributing goods and facilitating the movement of people to keep things running smoothly (Bakar et al., 2022). With increasing economic growth, individual mobility rises, and the demand for movement surpasses the capacity of available transportation infrastructure (Firdaus et al., 2021).

Bandung City is the capital of West Java Province, where the population's activities steadily increase each year, reaching 2,469,589 inhabitants (BPS-West Java, 2020), leading to various issues such as traffic congestion in and around the city. Additionally, Bandung City is adjacent to other areas, namely Cimahi City and West Bandung Regency, which serve as transportation hubs.

The Ministry of Transportation through the Directorate General of Land Transportation provides public transportation for Bandung City and its surroundings, namely the Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya (Ariostar et al., 2022). This public transportation system is a collaborative effort of the areas neighboring Bandung City, particularly those along the route of the Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya, such as Cimahi City and West Bandung Regency. Therefore, the presence of Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya, which commenced operations on December 27, is

expected to reduce the number of private vehicles, according to data from the Bandung City Transportation Agency, which indicates that the number of vehicles in Bandung City is almost equivalent to its population of 2.2 million units (Ariostar et al., 2022)

On the other hand, the persistently high number of private vehicles in Bandung City and its surroundings is an indication of the level of satisfaction and comfort with the services provided by Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya. The operational managers of Trans Metro Pasundan are expected to enhance services such as organized schedules, comfort at shelters and on buses, readiness of staff to assist users, and addressing user complaints. Public evaluation of these services can serve as a benchmark for satisfaction; hence efforts are needed to improve services to address these issues (Chikkabagewadi et al., 2022; Esmailpour et al., 2020).

Therefore, research is needed to assess the service quality of Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya Corridor 2 in relation to public satisfaction, with the aim of evaluating and improving the service to encourage more people to use Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya Corridor 2, thereby reducing the number of private vehicles and alleviating traffic congestion (Dwiatmoko et al., 2022; Isradi et al., 2022; Rachmadina et al., 2023).

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The objectives of this research are to evaluate the performance of Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya Corridor 2 based on indicators such as load factor, travel time, and Headway according to World Bank standards, as well as to analyze users' perceptions of their satisfaction levels and expectations based on Ministerial Regulation No. 29 of 2015. Furthermore, this research aims to identify the service conditions implemented on Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya Corridor 2 in accordance with the provisions stated in Ministerial Regulation No. 29 of 2015. Based on these aspects, this paper takes on the topic of "Analysis of Service Level of Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya Corridor 2 Based on Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) and Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI)".

II. RESEARCH METHOD

Generally, every research is conducted with a "research method" so that all processes that must be completed can be fulfilled as planned and the research can be concluded at the decision-making point (Sum et al., 2019). Direct observation, interviews, and questionnaires are used as primary data collection methods (Esmailpour et al., 2020; Suria et al., 2019). Research preparation involves several stages of work or methodology presented in the form of a flowchart (Dermawan et al., 2021), which can be seen in Figure 1. below.

Figure 1. Flowchart

The research took place along the route of Corridor 2 of Trans Metro Pasundan in Bandung. Below is the route of Corridor 2 of Trans Metro Pasundan Bandung Raya (Kota Baru Parahyangan – Alun-alun Kota Bandung):

Kota Baru Parahyangan – STEI LPPM A – RS. Karisma Cimareme A – RS. IMC A – Masjid Ar-Ridwan A – Padasuka Indah A – Ranca Belut A – PLN Cisangkan A – BRI – RSUD Cibabat A – Dinas Sosial – Jalan Budi – SMAN 13 A – Paledang – Rajawali Barat – Plaza Telkom Rajawali – Rajawali 1 – Dungus Cariang – SMA Trinitas – RS. Kebon Jati – SMA Pasundan – Perintis Kemerdekaan – Lembong – Alun-alun Kota Bandung – KEB Hana Bank – GKI Anugerah – Mayapada Tower – Toko Ambon – Kemenag Kanwil Jabar – Optik Krida – Sudirman 3 – Kebon Kopi – SMAN 13 B – Cilember – RS. Mitra Kasih – RSUD Cibabat B – SMPN 6 – Gedung 4 – Pasar Antri – Stasiun Cimahi – Lapangan Rajawali – Gedung 4 – Buana – PLN Cisangkan B – Ranca Belut B – Padasuka Indah B – Masjid Ar-Ridwan B – RS. IMC B – RS. Karisma Cimareme B – STEI LPPM B – Bale Pare – Kota Baru Parahyangan. The map of the route of Corridor 2 of Trans Metro Pasundan can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Research Location

The research will be conducted in the morning (06:30 – 08:00), afternoon (11:30-13:00), and evening (15:30-17:00) based on the results of the preliminary survey conducted over 3 days to determine the time for the research survey, as well as based on considerations and suggestions from the operational team of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2, namely PT. Surveyor Indonesia.

The data used in the calculation in this research includes primary and secondary data (Firdaus et al., 2022; Rifai et al., 2021). Primary data is obtained by conducting surveys directly at the research location, including:

1. Number of Passengers
2. Results of Questionnaire Completion
3. Travel Time
4. Headway
5. Operational Duration

Then, for secondary data obtained from relevant institutions as part of the research, the secondary data required in this

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study includes (Andriyani et al., 2021; Isradi, Farhan, et al., 2021; Isradi, Molina, et al., 2021):

1. Route Network Map
2. Number of Fleet

The load factor was obtained at 06:30, 11:30, and 15:30 on three days, namely May 23-25, 2023. A recapitulation is conducted to facilitate standardization with the World Bank to determine whether it is in accordance with the standards or not based on the field data obtained. Below is the recapitulation table of the load factor:

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Load Factor

Table 1. Recapitulation of Average Load Factor

Poll	Time	Capacity	Number of Stops	Total Passengers	Avg of Load factor (%)	Standar World Bank	Compliant/Not
A	06.30 (23 May 2023)	20	29	36	86.03	70%	Not Compliant
	06.30 (24 May 2023)	20	29	22	53.44	70%	Compliant
	06.30 (25 May 2023)	20	29	33	80.51	70%	Compliant
	11.30 (8 June 2023)	20	29	17	35.34	70%	Compliant
	15.30 (23 May 2023)	20	29	39	63.10	70%	Compliant
	15.30 (24 May 2023)	20	29	11	23.79	70%	Compliant
	15.30 (25 May 2023)	20	29	27	35.86	70%	Compliant
B	06.30 (23 May 2023)	20	28	32	87.03	70%	Not Compliant
	06.30 (24 May 2023)	20	28	17	28.51	70%	Compliant
	06.30 (25 May 2023)	20	28	33	38.14	70%	Compliant
	11.30 (7 June 2023)	20	28	18	62.22	70%	Compliant
	15.30 (23 May 2023)	20	28	38	60.92	70%	Compliant
	15.30 (24 May 2023)	20	28	26	72.59	70%	Not Compliant
	15.30 (25 May 2023)	20	28	37	94.07	70%	Not Compliant
Average					58	70%	Compliant

Based on Table 1, the highest average load factor (94.07%) is found at Poll B during the evening rush hour, while the lowest (23.79%) occurred at Poll A during the evening rush hour. The table indicates load factors outside the World Bank standards at certain times, for example, at Poll A at 06:30 on March 23, 2023, Poll B at 06:30 on March 23, 2024, and at 15:30 on March 24 and 25, 2024. Here is an example calculation of the load factor that occurred on May 23, 2023, from 06:30 to 08:00, from Rancabelut stop to PLN Cisangkan stop:

$$L_f = \frac{P_{sg}}{C} * 100\%$$

$$L_f = \frac{19}{20} * 100\%$$

$$L_f = 95\%$$

B. Travel Time

The average travel time of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 is calculated from a 5-day survey by recording travel times during the morning commute (06:30), midday (11:30), and evening rush hour (15:30) from Poll A at the Ikea stop to Poll B at the Alun-Alun Bandung stop.

Table 2. Travel Time of Trans Metro Pasundan 2

Poll	Waktu	Berangkat	Datang	Travel time	Jarak Tempuh	Standar World Bank	Compliant/Not
A	06.30 (23 May 2023)	06:30	07:52	81.68 Minute	23 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
	06.30 (24 May 2023)	06:30	07:46	76.32 Minute	23 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
	06.30 (25 May 2023)	06:30	08:00	89. 11 Minute	23 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
	11.30 (8 June 2023)	11:30	12:41	69.13 Minute	23 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant

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	15.30 (24 May 2023)	15:30	16:32	62.05 Minute	23 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
	15.30 (25 May 2023)	15:30	16:38	67.56 Minute	23 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
B	06.30 (23 May 2023)	06:30	07:34	60.4 Minute	21 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
	06.30 (24 May 2023)	06:30	07:30	59.43 Minute	21 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
	06.30 (25 May 2023)	06:30	07:40	70.22 Minute	21 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
	11.30 (7 June 2023)	11:30	12:35	65.12 Minute	21 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
	15.30 (23 May 2023)	15:30	17:02	91.55 Minute	21 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
	15.30 (24 May 2023)	15:30	16:58	88 Minute	21 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
	15.30 (25 May 2023)	15:30	17:00	90.01 Minute	21 Km	10-12 km/hour	Compliant
Rata-Rata					18 Km/hour	10-12 km/hour	Compliant

Based on Table 2, the longest travel time occurred on Trans Metro Pasundan Poll B during the evening rush hour on May 23, 2023 (91.55 minutes). This was due to heavy traffic from Alun-Alun Bandung to IKEA Kota Baru Parahyangan. The fastest travel time was recorded on Trans Metro Pasundan Poll B during the morning commute on May 24, 2023 (59.43 minutes). All travel times comply with the World Bank standards for the distance covered by Trans Metro Pasundan corridor. The calculation of travel time is provided below:
 $TTAB = (T_{AB}) / (J_{AB})$

$$TTAB = 23/1.22$$

$$TTAB = 18 \text{ Km/Hour}$$

C. Headway

The Headway value was obtained from the research results statically, the data were collected by recording the departure time of buses with the departure time of the next bus at the starting point at each Poll. Here is the Headway data obtained in the field on July 2-3.

Table 3. Recapitulation of Headway

Poll	Date	Headway (Mnt)	Avg	Standar World Bank	Compliant/Not
A	2 Juli 2023	0:09		10-20 Minute	Compliant
	3 Juli 2023	0:09		10-20 Minute	Compliant
B	2 Juli 2023	0:08		10-20 Minute	Compliant
	3 Juli 2023	0:09		10-20 Minute	Compliant

Based on Table 3, the average Headway obtained in the field at Poll A and Poll B on July 2-3, 2023 is in the range of 8-9 minutes. Therefore, the Headway values observed are still within the World Bank standard, with a maximum standard of 10-20 minutes.

D. Level of Satisfaction and Expectation Alignment

Assessment of passenger satisfaction level with the service of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 is used as an indicator for future improvements to enhance service quality. The assessment of satisfaction level of Trans Metro Pasundan

Corridor 2 consists of 45 attribute questions. Below is an example calculation of the average satisfaction level/Mean Satisfaction Score (MSS) for variable 1:

$$MSS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i}{n}$$

$$MSS = \frac{418}{105}$$

$$MSS = 3.981$$

For variable 1, the total score obtained from 105 questionnaire respondents is 418. Based on the calculation

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above, the average satisfaction score (MSS) for passengers of Trans Metro Pasundan services is 3.981.

Assessment of the expectation level of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services serves as a measure for service improvement efforts aimed at enhancing passenger satisfaction with Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services. Below is an example calculation of the average expectation level/Mean Importance Score (MIS) for variable 1:

$$MIS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i}{n}$$

$$MIS = \frac{474}{105}$$

$$MIS = 4.514$$

For variable 1, the total score obtained from 105 questionnaire respondents is 474. Based on the calculation

above, the average expectation score (MIS) for passengers of Trans Metro Pasundan services is 4.514.

Here is an example calculation of the Conformity Rate between satisfaction (MSS) and expectation (MIS) of passengers of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services for variable 1:

$$\text{Conformity Rate} = \frac{\text{MSS of avg}}{\text{MIS of avg}} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Conformity Rate} = \frac{3.981}{4.514} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Conformity Rate} = 88.186\%$$

Table 4. Conformity Rate of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 Services

No.	Variable	Question	Average Satisfaction (MSS)	Expected Average (MIS)	Conformity Rate (%)
1	Awak Kendaraan	How long does the bus stop at the shelter/bus stop?	3.981	4.514	88.186
2		What is the waiting time between buses?	3.500	4.400	79.545
3		Are employees ready on site when needed?	4.048	4.314	93.819
4		How is information on emergency handling procedures on the bus?	3.886	4.295	90.466
5		Are employees responsive to passenger needs?	3.981	4.305	92.478
6		What is the employee's ability to respond to passenger complaints?	3.924	4.362	89.956
7		What is the employee's ability to respond to suggestions from passengers?	3.848	4.295	89.579
8		How is the company's ability to respond quickly to passenger complaints?	3.676	4.229	86.937
9		How friendly is provided by the employees on the bus?	4.067	4.438	91.631
10		How polite are the employees on the bus?	4.219	4.467	94.456
11		What are the employee's skills in communicating with passengers?	3.810	4.343	87.719
12		How do employees provide information on bus arrivals clearly and communicatively?	3.838	4.410	87.041
13		What is the employee's ability to drive?	4.019	4.495	89.407
14	Sarana	How are seat facilities provided on Trans Metro Pasundan buses?	4.048	4.514	89.662
15		How are hand grip facilities provided on Trans Metro Pasundan buses?	4.210	4.390	95.879
16		How are lighting facilities provided on the bus?	4.086	4.400	92.857

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17		How is first aid equipment provided on Trans Metro Pasundan buses?	3.438	4.221	81.449
18	Sarana	How to provide fire extinguishers on Trans Metro Pasundan buses	4.114	4.324	95.154
19		How are safety belts provided on Trans Metro Pasundan buses?	3.629	4.219	86.005
20		How clean is the Trans Metro Pasundan Bus?	4.308	4.600	93.645
21		How are facilities available for submitting complaints and suggestions?	3.798	4.257	89.217
22		How is the availability of special seats for passengers with special needs and pregnant women?	3.981	4.410	90.281
23		How are the facilities provided at Trans Metro Pasundan shelters/stops? Example: lights?	2.581	4.419	58.405
24		How are waiting chairs provided at Trans Metro Pasundan shelters/stops?	2.962	4.442	66.675
25		How is the Greater Bandung city map provided at Trans Metro Pasundan shelters/stops?	2.990	4.467	66.951
26		How is the Trans Metro Pasundan route map provided at TMP shelters/stops?	3.114	4.429	70.323
27		How are ticket machines provided at Trans Metro Pasundan shelters/stops?	2.962	4.524	65.474
28		How are information boards provided at Trans Metro Pasundan shelters/stops?	2.810	4.495	62.500
29	Prasarana	What is the availability of Shelters/Stops?	3.143	4.448	70.664
30		How is Poll availability?	2.724	4.471	60.920
31		How many Trans Metro Pasundan shelters are there?	3.229	4.505	71.670
32	Kenyamanan	Providing AC facilities on Trans Metro Pasundan buses?	4.352	4.467	97.441
33		How are trash bins provided on Trans Metro Pasundan buses?	3.705	4.276	86.637
34		How comfortable is the Trans Metro Pasundan Bus?	4.200	4.429	94.839
35		How clean is the Trans Metro Pasundan Bus?	4.400	4.590	95.851
36		How many bus fleets operate?	3.810	4.429	86.022
37		How many routes does the Trans Metro Pasundan bus offer?	3.692	4.457	82.840
38		How easy is the Bus Friends application?	3.267	4.448	73.448
39		How is the cleanliness at the Trans Metro Pasundan shelter/stop?	2.743	4.286	64.000
40		How comfortable is the Trans Metro Pasundan shelter/stop?	2.838	4.505	63.002
41		How are trash bins provided in TMP shelters/stops?	2.933	4.476	65.532

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42	What are the prices for Pasundan Trans Metro Bus Tickets?	4.314	4.429	97.419
43	How far is the shelter from public places?	3.905	4.476	87.234
44	What are the smoking ban regulations?	3.800	4.457	85.256
45	How easy is it to get information about bus arrivals and bus delays?	3.562	4.467	79.744
Jumlah		164.441	198.592	3728.215
Rata-Rata		3.654	4.413	82.849

Presentation >100% can be said to indicate that the satisfaction with that attribute has exceeded passengers' expectations. Based on Table 4. it shows that the average Conformity Rate of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services is 82.849%, with a range of values between 58.405% for the attribute of providing facilities at Trans Metro Pasundan shelters/stops to 97.441% for the attribute of providing air conditioning facilities inside Trans Metro Pasundan buses.

E. Quadrant Analysis Using the Index Performance Analysis (IPA) Method on Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 Services

Below are the results of the analysis of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services using the Index Performance Analysis method, which can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 2. IPA Cartesian Diagram

Based on the Cartesian diagram of the Index Performance Analysis method on Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services, four quadrants are obtained, consisting of quadrant I, which is the improvement category, quadrant II, which is the satisfaction category, quadrant III, which is the dissatisfaction category, and quadrant IV, which is the no need for improvement category. Below are the attributes for each quadrant explained as follows:

1. Quadrant I, Improvement (Concentrate)

The condition of quadrant I indicates that attributes have low performance but are highly expected by passengers regarding the services of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2. Attributes included in quadrant I are: 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 38, 40, and 41.

2. Quadrant II, Satisfactory (Keep up with the good work)

The condition of quadrant II depicts attributes with high performance and high expectations from passengers regarding the services of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2. Attributes included in quadrant II are those that should be maintained. Attributes included in quadrant II are: 1, 3, 9, 10, 12, 13, 16, 20, 22, 32, 34, 35, 36, 37, 42, 43, 44, and 45.

3. Quadrant III, Dissatisfactory (Low priority)

The condition of quadrant III depicts attributes with low performance and low expectations from passengers regarding the services of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2. Attributes included in quadrant III are those that do not require high prioritization. Attributes included in quadrant III are: 17 and 39.

4. Quadrant IV, No Need for Improvement (Possible overkill)

The condition of quadrant IV depicts attributes with high performance but low expectations from passengers regarding the services of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2. Attributes included in quadrant IV are those that are excessive in their provision. Attributes included in quadrant IV are: 4, 6, 7, 8, 11, 14, 15, 18, 19, 21, and 33.

F. Analysis of Customer Satisfaction Index for Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 Services

To obtain the Customer Satisfaction Index for Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services, it is obtained through the following steps:

The median score of Satisfaction level for each attribute is obtained from the average attribute Satisfaction or mean (MSS). Here is an example calculation of the average satisfaction level/Mean Satisfaction Score (MSS) for variable 1:

$$SS = \frac{\sum_i^n X_i}{n}$$

$$MSS = \frac{418}{105}$$

$$MSS = 3.981$$

The median score of the expectation level for each attribute is obtained from the average attribute expectation or mean

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(MIS). Here is an example calculation of the average expectation level/Mean Importance Score (MIS) for variable 1:

$$MIS = \frac{\sum_i^n Y_i}{n}$$

$$MIS = \frac{474}{105}$$

$$MIS = 4.514$$

The Importance Weighting Factor (WF) for each attribute is obtained by dividing the median score of the expectation level by the average attribute performance level. Here is an example calculation to find the WF value for variable 1:

$$WF = \frac{MIS_i \text{ (var 1)}}{\sum_i^p MIS_i} * 100\%$$

$$WF = \frac{4.514}{198.592}$$

$$WF = 0.023$$

The Weighted Score (WS) for each attribute is obtained by multiplying the Importance Weighting Factor by the median

score of the Satisfaction level. Here is an example calculation to find the WS value for variable 1:

$$WS = MSS_i \times WF$$

$$WS = 3.981 \times 0.023$$

$$WS = 0.090$$

The Customer Satisfaction Index is obtained by dividing the total Weighted Score by the highest possible score, which is 5. Here is the calculation to find the Customer Satisfaction Index value:

$$CSI = \frac{\sum_i^p WSi}{HS} * 100\%$$

$$CSI = \frac{3.654}{5} * 100\%$$

$$CSI = 73.078\%$$

Here is the recapitulation of the calculation results for the Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI), as shown in the table below.

Table 5. Calculation of Customer Satisfaction Index for Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 Services

No.	Mean Satisfaction Score (MSS)	Mean Importance Score (MIS)	Importance Weighting Factor (WF)	Weighted Score (WS)
1	3.981	4.514	0.023	0.090
2	3.500	4.400	0.022	0.078
3	4.048	4.314	0.022	0.088
4	3.886	4.295	0.022	0.084
5	3.981	4.305	0.022	0.086
6	3.924	4.362	0.022	0.086
7	3.848	4.295	0.022	0.083
8	3.676	4.229	0.021	0.078
9	4.067	4.438	0.022	0.091
10	4.219	4.467	0.022	0.095
11	3.810	4.343	0.022	0.083
12	3.838	4.410	0.022	0.085
13	4.019	4.495	0.023	0.091
14	4.048	4.514	0.023	0.092
15	4.210	4.390	0.022	0.093
16	4.086	4.400	0.022	0.091
17	3.438	4.221	0.021	0.073
18	4.114	4.324	0.022	0.090
19	3.629	4.219	0.021	0.077
20	4.308	4.600	0.023	0.100
21	3.798	4.257	0.021	0.081
22	3.981	4.410	0.022	0.088
23	2.581	4.419	0.022	0.057
24	2.962	4.442	0.022	0.066
25	2.990	4.467	0.022	0.067
26	3.114	4.429	0.022	0.069

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27	2.962	4.524	0.023	0.067
28	2.810	4.495	0.023	0.064
29	3.143	4.448	0.022	0.070
30	2.724	4.471	0.023	0.061
31	3.229	4.505	0.023	0.073
32	4.352	4.467	0.022	0.098
33	3.705	4.276	0.022	0.080
34	4.200	4.429	0.022	0.094
35	4.400	4.590	0.023	0.102
36	3.810	4.429	0.022	0.085
37	3.692	4.457	0.022	0.083
38	3.267	4.448	0.022	0.073
39	2.743	4.286	0.022	0.059
40	2.838	4.505	0.023	0.064
41	2.933	4.476	0.023	0.066
42	4.314	4.429	0.022	0.096
43	3.905	4.476	0.023	0.088
44	3.800	4.457	0.022	0.085
45	3.562	4.467	0.022	0.080
Total	164.441	198.592	1.000	3.654
Customer Satisfaction Indeks (CSI)				73.078

Based on Table 5, the Customer Satisfaction Index for Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services is 73.078, which falls within the interval of 66.00-80.99 in Table 2.5. This indicates that passengers are "Satisfied" with the performance of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services. Below are the results of the analysis of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services using the Performance Index method.

G. Summary of Calculation Result

Based on the calculation results measuring the performance of Trans Metro Pasundan, where the average load factor performance is 58%, travel time is 18.85 km/hour, and Headway is 9 minutes, these values are in accordance with the standards set by the World Bank, as shown in Table 4.28. Furthermore, the IPA and CSI values obtained are 82% and 73%, respectively, which can be considered compliant with the standards set by Ministerial Regulation No. 29 of 2015, as shown in the table below.

Table 6. Recapitulation of Performance, IPA, and CSI of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2

No.	Variable	Average Actual Value	Standard Value	Standard	Compliant/Not
1.	Load factor	58%	Max 70%	World Bank	Compliant
2.	Travel time	18.85 Km/hour	Min 10-12 Km/hour	World Bank	Compliant
3.	Headway	9 Minute	Max 10-20 Minute	World Bank	Compliant
4.	Index Performance Analysis	82%	Min 80%	Peraturan Menteri No. 29 Tahun 2015	Compliant
5.	Customer Satisfaction Index	73%	66-80.99%	Peraturan Menteri No. 29 Tahun 2015	Compliant

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis and discussion in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Operational performance of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2: The highest load factor was recorded at

Poll B at 15:30 (94.07%), while the lowest was at Poll A at 15:30 (23.79%). The longest travel time occurred at Poll B at 15:30 on May 23, 2023 (91.55 minutes) due to heavy traffic. Some load factors do not meet the World Bank standards, for example, at

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Poll A at 06:30 on March 23, 2023. However, travel time complies with the standards for distances of 21 km and 23 km (10-12 km per hour). Headway between 5-13 minutes meets the standard (10-20 minutes).

2. Perceptions of passenger satisfaction and expectations for Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 based on attributes with scores below 80% include: provision of facilities at shelters/stops, availability of Polls, provision of information boards, comfort, cleanliness, ticket machine availability, garbage bins, waiting seats, city maps, route maps, shelter availability, number of shelters, ease of use of the Bus Friend application, and waiting time between buses. Attributes in quadrant I are the top priority for improvement, including facility provision, waiting seats, city maps, route maps, ticket machines, information boards, shelter availability, Poll availability, number of shelters, ease of use of the Bus Friend application, comfort, and garbage bins. These 12 attributes have a significant impact on passenger satisfaction and must be improved.
3. Evaluation of service conditions based on the Customer Satisfaction Index value for Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services is 73.078, which falls within the interval of 66.00-80.99, indicating that passengers are "Satisfied" with the performance of Trans Metro Pasundan Corridor 2 services.

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